

SURVEY OF HEALTH BENEFITS OF INTEGRATING MARTIAL ARTS INTO JUNIOR SECONDARY SCHOOL CURRICULUM IN AMAC, ABUJA, NIGERIA.

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This study explores the health benefits of integrating martial arts into the school curriculum for Junior Secondary School students in Abuja Municipal Area Council (AMAC), Abuja. Education is seen as key tool for nation-building, and martial arts examined for their potential to shape students' physical, mental, and emotional development. The research adopted descriptive survey design, involving 50 Physical and Health Education teachers from 10 selected public and private junior secondary schools. The study reviewed relevant literature on martial arts, their classifications, the concept of curriculum, and integration challenges. Data were collected using structured questionnaire. Results indicated that integrating martial arts into the curriculum significantly improved students' physical fitness and overall health, with mean scores above 2.5 and statistically significant at t-values ($p \leq 0.05$). However, perceptions of martial arts impacted on mental health, self-esteem, and emotional well-being were initially negative among teachers, with mean scores below 2.5. Despite this, hypothesis testing confirmed significant positive impacts in these areas. Long-term exposure to martial arts was also found to positively influence students' adoption of healthy lifestyles positively. The study concludes that martial arts offer significant health benefits and recommends their inclusion in the school curriculum to enhance physical fitness, mental health, and emotional well-being among junior secondary students in AMAC, Abuja.

Keywords: Health Benefits, Integrating Material Arts, School Curriculum

Introduction

Integration of martial arts into the school curriculum for junior secondary school students in the Abuja Municipal Area Council (AMAC) presents a significant opportunity to enhance the overall health and well-being of adolescents. Many educators and policymakers remain skeptical about the practicality and relevance of incorporating martial arts into the academic framework, often favouring traditional sports or academic pursuits over holistic approaches to students' health. The study investigated the health benefits of integrating martial arts into the school curriculum for junior secondary school students in AMAC, Abuja, while addressing the existing barriers to implementation. By exploring the perceptions of students, parents, and educators regarding martial arts, as well as assessing the potential impact on physical fitness, mental health, and social skills. Also, the research sought to provide evidence-based recommendations for policymakers and educational stakeholders to enhance the curriculum and foster a healthier school environment for adolescents.

Specifically, the objectives of the study include to:

- i. evaluate how integrating martial arts into the school curriculum improves the physical fitness and overall health of junior secondary school students in AMAC, Abuja,
- ii. to investigate the impact of martial arts on the mental health, self-esteem, and emotional well-being of students in AMAC, Abuja, and
- iii. analyze whether early exposure of junior secondary school students to martial arts influences long-term healthy lifestyle choices, such as regular exercise and healthy eating of students in AMAC, Abuja.

Education is fundamental to empowering students by teaching them how to interact with others, understand academic content, and engage with concepts that foster personal growth. It involves the transmission of knowledge, attitudes, competencies, and norms that help individuals integrate into a specific culture or reshape societal values (Adegboyega, 2019). According to Ujuagu, Uzor, Igwilo, and Akpu (2020), the term *curriculum* originates from the Latin word *curare*, meaning "race course," and refers to the structured experiences and activities that guide children toward maturity. It encompasses the courses and content provided by educational institutions and is typically prescriptive, based on a general

syllabus that outlines required subjects and expected levels of understanding for each grade or standard. Thus, all the courses offered by a school collectively represent its curriculum (Ujuagu et al., 2020). Kelly (2018) defined curriculum as all learning organized and directed by the school, whether conducted individually or in groups, inside or outside the classroom. It sets educational goals and the methods to achieve them. Similarly, Offorma (2015) described curriculum as a planned learning experience offered to students, comprising three key components: a study programme, an activity programme, and a guidance program. Consequently, the definition of curriculum has evolved to meet the diverse needs of academic programmes.

The term "martial arts" is generally used to describe the various combative arts that are studied around the world. Translated to 'military arts', they stem from the need to protect one's self against an enemy's attack, or to escape a dangerous situation. They have always been linked to physical development but are also used to enhance character and spiritual development (Gill, 2015). One example of this is the increase in participation for family development over the last 30 years to enhance self-confidence, moral development and life preparation (Hernandez & Anderson, 2015). Martial arts encompass both internal and external philosophies, with values such as sportsmanship, honour, pacifism, nationalism, sacrifice, and civic duty representing internal philosophies (Werner-Siedler et al., 2017). The practice of martial arts integrates various ideologies, religions, and ethical systems, such as Zen and Taoism, particularly in styles like Aikido, Judo, Karate, and Kendo. Concepts from Zen and Taoism, such as mindfulness and quiet, align with modern health ideas. Philosophically, martial arts are believed to foster personal growth and a sense of mastery and success. This aligns with Bandura's theory that mastery experiences positively influence self-efficacy (Grotan, Sund, & Bjerkeset, 2019).

When examining the implementation of the Physical and Health Education (PHE) component of the Basic Science and Technology Curriculum, factors such as policy issues, PHE objectives, availability of facilities, equipment, professional qualifications, instructional materials, in-service training, teaching abilities, and students' attitudes towards PHE must be considered (Ovbiebo, Lator, & Ogbouma, 2022). Abubakar, Rabi, Usman, and

Yahaya (2015) identified four dimensions of curriculum fidelity: adherence, exposure, quality of delivery, and participant responsiveness. To ensure the curriculum's success, policies should be implemented to guide its objectives, including rules, schedules, resources, and health and safety (CAR-ICOM, 2011). Effective implementation of PHE and sports programmes, both instructional and extracurricular, is crucial for enhancing sports performance and development in Nigeria (Abubakar et al., 2015). The study equally assessed the health benefits of integrating martial arts into the school curriculum for junior secondary students in AMAC, Abuja.

Methodology

The design of this study is descriptive survey. It is aimed at providing the opinions of the respondents on the Health Benefits of Integrating Martial Art into the School Curriculum of Junior Secondary School Students in AMAC, Abuja. According to Disman, Ali and Barliana (2017), descriptive survey research design is the plan of study which aims at collecting data on the topic and describing in a systematic way, the characteristics and features of facts about a given population. The population of the study Junior Secondary Schools comprises Physical and Health Education (PHE) Teachers within Abuja Municipal Area Council (AMAC). Purposive and simple random sampling procedures were used in selecting the required sample for this study. Purposive sampling was used in this study in selecting 50 Junior Secondary Schools Physical and Health Education (PHE) Teachers from six Public Junior Secondary Schools and four Private Junior Secondary Schools within AMAC.

Research Questions

The following research questions were formulated to guide the study:

1. Does integration of martial art into the school curriculum improves the physical fitness and overall health of junior secondary school students in AMAC, Abuja?
2. What is the impact of martial arts on the mental health, self-esteem, and emotional well-being of students in AMAC, Abuja?
3. Does early exposure of junior secondary school students to martial arts influence long-term healthy lifestyle choices, such as regular exercise and healthy eating of students in AMAC, Abuja?

Research Justification

The current curriculum in AMAC schools often overlooks the importance of physical activity and mental resilience, contributing to rising concerns about childhood obesity, mental health issues, and the overall lack of physical fitness among students. Many junior secondary school students face challenges such as sedentary lifestyles, academic pressure, and social anxieties, which can adversely affect their health and academic performance. The absence of structured programs that promote physical activity and mental well-being leaves a gap in the educational framework that could be effectively addressed through martial arts training.

Null Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were formulated and tested at $P \leq 0.05$ levels of significance.

H₀₁: The integration martial art into the school curriculum does not improve the physical fitness and overall health of junior secondary school students in AMAC, Abuja.

H₀₂: Integration of Martial Arts into the Junior Secondary School Curriculum has no impact on the mental health, self-esteem and emotional well-being of the students.

H₀₃: Early exposure of junior secondary school students to martial arts does not influence long-term healthy lifestyle choices, such as regular exercise and healthy eating of students in AMAC, Abuja.

Results

Research Question One: Does integration of martial art into the school curriculum improves the physical fitness and overall health of junior secondary school students in AMAC, Abuja?

Table 1.0: Mean Scores for how Integration of Martial Arts into the School Curriculum can improve the Physical Fitness and Overall Health of Junior Secondary School Students in AMAC, Abuja

Items	N	Mean	S.D	Df	t ^{Cal.}	t ^{Tab.}	Decision
1 Martial arts training can improve Junior Students' physical strength.	50	3.31	1.15				
2 Participating in martial arts can enhanced students' endurance and stamina.	50	3.71	0.76				
3 Martial arts training can positively affect students' mental health and well-being.	50	3.41	0.94	49	53.86	51.833	Accepted
4 Students can experience fewer health issues if they are practicing martial arts	50	3.06	0.98				
5 Martial arts can teach students techniques to manage stress better.	50	3.73	0.74				

Source: Field Work (2025)

Table 1.0 shows the results of how integration of martial arts into the school curriculum can improve the physical fitness and overall health of junior secondary school students in AMAC, Abuja. All the items harmonically obtained mean scores above 2.50. This means that almost all the PHE teachers in the study area accepted that the listed items were outcomes of how integration of martial arts into the school curriculum can improve the physical fitness and overall health of junior secondary school students in AMAC, Abuja

Research Question Two: What is the impact of martial arts on the mental health, self-esteem, and emotional well-being of students in AMAC, Abuja?

Table 2.0: Mean Scores for the Impact of Martial Arts on the Mental Health, Self-esteem, and Emotional Well-being of Students in AMAC, Abuja.

Items	N	Mean	S.D	Df	t ^{Cal.}	t ^{Tab.}	Decision
1 Practicing martial arts can improve students' ability to focus and concentrate.	50	3.31	1.15				
2 Martial arts can provide students with effective ways to manage their emotions.	50	3.71	0.76				
3 Students' self-confidence can increase as a result of participating in martial arts.	50	3.41	0.94	49	59.39	1.833	Accepted
4 Martial arts can help students feel more capable of achieving their goals.	50	3.06	0.98				
5 Students can feel happier and more satisfied with their life if they are participating in martial arts.	50	3.73	0.74				

Source: Field Work (2025)

Table 2.0 shows the results of the impact of martial arts on the mental health, self-esteem, and emotional well-being of students in AMAC, Abuja. All the items harmonically obtained mean scores above 2.50. This is an indication that all the junior secondary school PHE teachers in the study area accepted that the item were the impact of martial arts on the mental health, self-esteem, and emotional well-being of students in AMAC, Abuja.

Research Question Three: Does early exposure of junior secondary school students to martial arts influences long-term healthy lifestyle choices, such as regular exercise and healthy eating of students in AMAC, Abuja?

Table 3.0: Mean Scores for Influence of Long-term Exposure of Junior Secondary School Students to Martial Arts on the Healthy Lifestyle of the Students in Abuja Municipal Area Council.

Items	N	Mean	S.D	Df	t ^{-Cal.}	t ^{-Tab.}	Decision
1 Martial arts can motivate students to engage in regular physical exercise.	50	3.71	0.80				
2 Involvement in martial arts can encourage students to make healthier food choices.	50	3.15	1.11				
3 Martial arts can influence students to eat balanced meals that support their physical fitness.	50	2.89	1.11	49	61.3191	1.833	Accepted
4 Early exposure to martial arts can make students more likely to prioritize a healthy lifestyle as they grow older.	50	3.16	1.11				
5 Early martial arts training can shape students' views on the importance of a healthy lifestyle.	50	3.70	0.80				

Source: Field Work (2025)

Table 3.0 shows the result of influence of long-term exposure of junior secondary school students to Martial Arts on the healthy lifestyle of the Students in Abuja Municipal Area Council. All the items five, obtained mean scores above 2.50. This is an indication that all the respondents accepted that; all the listed items were influence of long-term exposure of junior secondary school students to Martial Arts on the healthy lifestyle of the Students in Abuja Municipal Area Council.

Discussion

The findings of the study revealed the Health Benefits of Integrating Martial Art into the School Curriculum of Junior Secondary School Students in AMAC, Abuja.

Research question one aimed to determine how integrating martial arts into the school curriculum improves the physical fitness and overall health of

junior secondary school students in AMAC, Abuja. The findings revealed that, martial arts training enhances students' physical strength, endurance, stamina, mental health, well-being, and stress management, while reducing health issues. The t-test results ($t=53.865$, $\text{Sig}=0.000$, $p\leq 0.05$) indicated agreement among Physical and Health Education (PHE) teachers that, martial arts integration improves students' physical and mental health. These findings align with Benjamin's (2021) similar report.

Research question two analyzed the impact of martial arts on students' mental health, self-esteem, and emotional well-being in AMAC, Abuja. The findings revealed a significant positive impact, with all items surpassing the cut-off mean score of 2.50. The t-test results ($t=59.399$, $\text{Sig}=0.000$, $p\leq 0.05$) confirmed this impact, leading to the rejection of the null hypothesis and acceptance of the alternate hypothesis. This finding is consistent with Fuller and Lloyd's (2020) study on martial arts and well-being

Research question three examined the influence of long-term exposure to martial arts on the healthy lifestyle of junior secondary school students, in AMAC, Abuja. The findings showed a significant influence, with all items surpassing the cut-off mean score of 2.50. The t-test results ($t=61.319$, $\text{Sig}=0.000$, $p\leq 0.05$) confirmed this influence, leading to the rejection of the null hypothesis and acceptance of the alternate hypothesis. This aligns with the findings of Grotan, Sund, and Bjerkeset (2019) in their study on mental health and academic self-efficacy.

Conclusions

The current study was carried out to investigate the Health Benefits of Integrating Martial Art into the School Curriculum of Junior Secondary School Students in AMAC, Abuja. The study indicated that there was significant Health Benefits of Integrating Martial Art into the School Curriculum of Junior Secondary School Students in AMAC, Abuja

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